

Rs. 10.00 Annual Rs. 100.00

SOCIAL WELFARE

ISSN : 0037-8038

Vol. 66 No.01

April, 2019

Education Key to Women's Empowerment

SOCIAL WELFARE

ISSN 0037-8038 Vol. 66 No.01 April 2019

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Editor
Manjit Singh

Editorial & Business Office

Central Social Welfare Board

*Dr. Durgabai Deshmukh
Samaj Kalyan Bhawan*

**B-12, Qutub Institutional Area
New Delhi-110 603**

Phones: 26543747, 26543753

Fax : 91-11-26960057

Website : www.cswb.gov.in

email : editorsw@rediffmail.com

For magazine related enquiries :
e-mail : businessunit782@gmail.com
Phone : 26543700/Extn : 782

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Single Copy	₹ 10/-
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Combined Subscription of Social Welfare & Samaj Kalyan	₹ 160/-
Life Membership	₹ 1000/-
Combined Life Membership	₹ 1600/-

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A Study of Investment Preference of Rural Working Women with Reference to Namakkal District

Dr. A. Dharmendran, Dr.C.Gowthaman

Abstract

The research study is focused on the analysis of investment preference of rural working women. With that the research determines Women's awareness about different avenue & the factors affect their investment decision. Today women are mainly self satisfactory and support to invest their income in a proper way to financially secure the family's future. Women are energetically participating in all activities such as education, politics, media, science and technology and becoming financial independent. With a shifting scenario, women has started energetically participating in investing their additional money still it all depends upon the different parameters such as degree of their risk taking capacity, influence of family members and friends and the dare to get exposed to present and modern investment avenues.

The study is based on personal interviews with rural working woman employees using a structured questionnaire. The study is based on primary data which are collected by distribution of a close ended questionnaire. The data has been analyzed using percentage analysis and Garrett's ranking technique. The researcher has found that rural working woman employees consider the safety as well as a high return on investment, on regular basis.

Keywords: Income, Savings, Investment, Rural Working Women,

"You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women".

-Jawaharlal Nehru.

I. Introduction

There are variety types of investment avenues presented in the market such as shares, debentures, mutual funds, bank deposits, life insurance, precious metal, public provident fund, post office saving schemes and many more. Some investment avenues are risky and some are risk free. The investors prefer to invest in particular Investment Avenue according to their need, risk bearing capacity and estimated return. When the investors would like high return they have to desire the investment avenue that is risky. Compared to females prefer to invest in investment avenues that are risky. The women with less education prefer to invest in risk-free investment avenues. The unmarried women prefer to invest in investment avenues where high risk is involved. Investment is one of the major issues of the married women as their small savings of today is to meet the expenses for the future.

Investment refers to the assurance of funds at present, in expectation of some positive rate of return in future. Today the possibility of investment is positively wide. An investor is confronted with an array of investment avenues as mentioned earlier. The income earned by an individual is partly exhausted and the rest is saved for meeting future expenses. As a substitute of keeping the savings idle people may like to use their savings to get returns on it in the future, which is known as 'investment'. A Portfolio is a combination of different investment assets mixed and matched for the purpose of achieving an investor's goal.

II. Objectives of The Study

1. To study the socio-economic conditions of the rural working women.
2. To study the investment pattern and preferences of rural working women in the study area.
3. To know the sources of information of motivation for rural working women

III. Research Methodology

1. **Collection of Data:** The study is focused on collection of primary as well as secondary data.

a) **Primary Data:** Questionnaire method.

b) **Secondary Data:**

- Existing reports.
- Books.
- Journals and magazines.
- Websites.

2. **Sampling method:** Non-probability sampling method - Convenience Sampling.

3. **Area of the study:** The study is based on the respondents in Namakkal District.

4. **Analysis of Data:**

- Simple percentage analysis.
- Garrett's ranking Technique.

IV. Limitations of the Study

1. Only women investors' have been taken in to consideration.
2. The study area is confined only to the Namakkal district.
3. The sample size is restricted to one hundred and fifty only.

V. Review of Literature

1. Meenakshi Chaturvedi and Shruti Khare (2012) analyses and suggests that there is an explosion in the growth of middle class families due to double income and increase in number of working women. There is a dire need to initiate steps to inculcate saving habit among the growing middle class families. The savings are to be pooled and channelized into productive investments. Hence effort should be made to attract women investors by providing right information and knowledge about the market through advertisement.
2. V.R.Palanivelu and K.Chandrakumar(2013) examined "the Investment choices of salaried class in Namakkal Taluk, Tamilnadu, India" with the help of 100 respondents as a sample size and it reveals that as per Income level of the employees and investment in different

avenues. Age factor is also important while doing investments.

3. According to Prof. Priya Vasagadekar's research (2014) on working women she conclude that because of high level education, today's women are getting the best job offers with high take home pay packages. It has become the present day need for working women in India to increase their wealth. As most of the women are low in financial literacy, it becomes hardly possible for them to manage their portfolios on their own. Also the risk bearing capacity of working women in India is low. This is due to lack of sound financial knowledge.
4. Dr.G.Shanthi and R. Murugesan (2016) "Investment preferences of salaried women employees" the study concluded that women investor still prefers to invest in financial products which give risk free returns. This confirms that Indian investors even if they are of high income, well educated, salaried, independent are conservative investors prefer to play safe.

VI. Data Analysis Interpretation

(A) Analysis of Demographic Factors of Respondents

1. Sex

All the respondents studied in this study are rural working women.

2. Age

Sl. No.	Age	Respondents	Percentage
1.	20-30	39	26.00
2.	31-40	47	31.33
3.	41-50	29	19.33
4.	51-60	24	16.00
5.	Above 60	11	07.34
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is clear from table 1 that 26 percent of the respondents belong to 20 to 30 age group, 31.33 percent of respondents belong to age group of 31 to 40. 19.33 percent of the respondents belong to 41 to 50 age group, 16 percent of respondents belong to 51 to 60 age group, and 07.34 percent of respondents belong to above 60 age group. Hence it is evident that majority of respondents belong

to the middle age group of 20-40, 57.33 percent which constitutes rural working women.

3. Education

Table - 2: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Education	Respondents	Percentage
1.	8th level	19	12.67
2.	SSLC	33	22.00
3.	HSc	42	28.00
4.	Degree	27	18.00
5.	Post Graduate	12	08.00
6.	Professional	17	11.33
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table 2 depicts that 12.67 percent of the investors have completed their 8th Standard level, 22 percent of the investor have SSLC, 28 percent of the respondents are HSc, 18 percent of the respondents are degree, 8 percent of the respondents are post graduate, and 11.33 percent of the respondents are professionally qualified.

4. Occupation

Table - 3: Occupation of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Occupation	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Private Sector	29	19.33
2.	Government Sector	34	22.66
3.	Co-Operative Sector	19	12.66
4.	Spinning Mills	08	05.33
5.	Supermarket	22	14.66
6.	Owen Business	11	07.33
7.	Others Jobs	27	18.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is clear from the table 3 that out of the 150 respondents, 19.33 percent of the investors are working in Private Sector whereas 22.66 percent are working in Government sector, 12.66 percent are Cooperative sector, 5.33 percent are in Spinning Mills, 14.66 percent are in Supermarket, 7.33 percent are Owen business and 18 percent are in other jobs like retailing, tailoring, etc. as shown in Table 3.

5. Marital Status

Table - 4: Marital Status of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Marital Status	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Un Married	49	32.67
2.	Married	83	55.33
3.	Divorced	7	04.67
4.	Widow	11	07.33
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is observed from table 4, that majority 55.33 percent of the respondents are married, 32.67 percent are unmarried, and 4.67 percent are divorced. 7.33 percent of widowed.

6. Family Background

Table - 5: Family Type of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Type of Family	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Single	18	12.00
2.	Joint Family	24	16.00
3.	Nuclear Family	108	72.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is understood from above table 5 that a majority 72 percent of the respondents is living in Nuclear family system. 16 percent of respondents imply that the joint family system and 12 percent of the respondents is single.

7. Monthly Income

Table - 6: Distribution of the Respondents According to their Monthly Income

Sl. No.	Monthly Income	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Rs. 5001- Rs. 10,000	31	20.67
2.	Rs. 10,001- Rs. 15,000	54	36.00
3.	Rs. 15,001- Rs. 20,000	29	19.33
4.	Rs. 20,001- Rs. 25,000	21	14.00
5.	Rs. 25,001- Rs. 30,000	15	10.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 6 that the monthly income of 20.67 percent of the rural working women under the study area between Rs. 5001 to Rs. 10,000. Only 36 percent of the rural working women earn monthly income between Rs. 10,001 to Rs. 15,000, 19.33 percent women were gets in monthly income between Rs. 15,001 to Rs. 20,000, 14 percent of women get a monthly income

between Rs. 20,001 to Rs. 25,000 and only 10 percent of women get in monthly income between Rs. 25,001 to Rs. 30,000.

The rural working women average monthly income Rs. 14,850, it is varied from Rs.5, 565 (37.47%).

8. Monthly Saving

Table - 7: Monthly Saving of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Monthly Saving	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Rs. 200- Rs. 300	44	29.33
2.	Rs. 301- Rs. 400	65	43.33
3.	Rs. 401- Rs. 500	19	12.67
4.	Rs. 501- Rs. 600	12	08.00
5.	Rs. 601- Rs. 700	10	06.67
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 7 that the monthly savings of 29.33 percent of the rural working women under the study area between Rs. 200 to Rs. 300. Only 43.33 percent of the women monthly saving were between Rs. 301 to Rs. 400, 12.67 percent women monthly saving were between Rs. 401 to Rs. 500, 8 percent of women monthly saving were between Rs. 501 to Rs. 600 and only 6.67 percent of women monthly saving were between Rs. 601 to Rs. 700.

The rural working women average monthly saving Rs. 369, it is varied from Rs.66 (17.88%).

9. Source of Information

Table - 8: Sources of Information about Various Investments

Sl. No.	Source of Information	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Friends	19	12.67
2.	Relatives	13	08.67
3.	Co-worker	21	14.00
4.	Local Cit Fund Advertisement	17	11.33
5.	Brokers / Agent	16	10.67
6.	Banking Awareness Camp	22	14.66
7.	News Papers	15	10.00
8.	Family Members	27	18.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is observed from table 8 that, among the different sources of investment information 12.67 percent of the respondents get information through friends, 8.67 percent of the respondents get information from relatives, 14 percent get information through co-workers, 11.33 percent of the respondents get information through local cit fund advertisement, 10.67 percent of the respondents get information through brokers/ agent, 14.66 percent of the respondents get information through banking awareness camp, 10 percent of the respondents get information through news papers and 18 percent of the respondents get information through family members. From the above table, it is clear that most of the investors dependent on the family members, friends and relatives for their investment idea.

(B) Preferences of the Investors

There are so many investment avenues available in the market, so the investors have to take investment decision very carefully. A study is made to identify their investment preference. The following tables display the investment options and objectives.

1. Investment of Savings

Table - 9: Preference for Investment of Savings

Sl. No.	Investment avenues	Rrespondents	Percentage
1.	Bank Deposit (RD,FD)	32	21.33
2.	Post office	17	11.34
3.	Insurance	15	10.00
4.	Gold/Silver/ Costly Stones	14	09.33
5.	Real Estates	12	08.00
6.	Local Cit Fund	24	16.00
7.	Tax Free Bonds/NSC	11	07.33
8.	Construction of own Buildings/ Separate House	25	16.67
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is above from the table 9 that, among the different type of investment 42.67 percent of the respondents invest in money for bank, post office and insurance. 9.33 percent of respondents invest their money in gold /silver/costly stones,

8 percent of the respondents invest their money in real estate, 16 percent invest their money local cit fund, 07.33 percent of the respondents invest their money in tax free bonds/NSC and 16.67 percent of the respondents invest their money in construction of own buildings/ separate house.

2. Objectives of the Investments

Table - 10: Objectives of the Investments

Sl. No	Objectives	Ranks										Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
1.	High return	3	6	3	41	18	2	31	15	22	9	150
2.	Future family security	8	32	10	10	13	14	15	20	14	14	150
3.	Tax benefit	10	6	11	18	23	6	21	19	17	19	150
4.	Children's education	5	18	12	16	20	25	19	8	17	10	150
5.	Children's marriage	68	7	31	4	3	7	3	11	9	7	150
6.	Personal safety	7	11	10	30	40	18	10	5	6	13	150
7.	Emergency need	9	24	11	10	7	26	11	20	18	14	150
8.	Retirement plans	8	18	8	9	10	22	22	20	12	21	150
9.	Meet Future Expenses	8	20	10	7	11	13	14	19	23	25	150
10.	Earning profit	24	8	44	5	5	17	4	13	12	18	150
	Total	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

Source: Primary Data

For analyzing the reasons for choosing the job by the workers. Garrett's ranking technique is used.

Sl. No.	Objectives	Total Score	Avg. Score	Rank
1.	High return	6861	45.74	VII
2.	Future family security	7430	49.53	IV
3.	Tax benefit	6828	45.52	IX
4.	Children's education	7307	48.71	V
5.	Children's marriage	9573	63.82	I
6.	Personal safety	7611	50.74	III
7.	Emergency need	7214	48.09	VI
8.	Retirement plans	6849	45.66	VIII
9.	Meet Future Expenses	6719	44.79	X
10.	Earning profit	7928	52.85	II

It is clear from the table 10 respondents have given the first and second predilection Children's marriage and Earning profit respectively. Remaining Third, Fourth and Fifth ranks are given to personal safety, Future family security and Children's education. It reveals that they are investment for rural working women such as Emergency need, High return, Retirement plans, Tax benefit and Meet Future Expenses

VII. Findings

1. Majority 47 (31.33%) of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years.
2. Among the sample investors, majority 42 (28%) of the respondents have studied up to high school.
3. Most 34 (22.66%) of the respondent are come under Government sector employee.
4. The study reveals that most 83 (55.33%) of the investors belong to married women.
5. Majority 108 (72%) of the respondents belong to nuclear family.
6. It is understood that most of the investors have a monthly income of Rs.10, 001 to Rs.15, 000.
7. Most of the investors have a monthly savings of Rs.301 to Rs.400 with 65 (43.33%).
8. The different sources of investment information 27 (18%) of the respondents get information through family members
9. Most of the investors have made their investment in bank deposits and followed by construction of own buildings/ separate house. in the study area.
10. On applying Garratt's ranking analysis relating to objectives of the investments, it is inferred that the most of the women investors have given the first rank to 'children's marriage', the second rank to 'earning profit', third rank to 'personal safety'.

VIII. Conclusion

The conclusion is made here based on the findings of the study. The highest percentage of women investors are in the age group of 31 to

40 years. The study revealed that postgraduate education among the rural woman investors is very less. Hence, effective schemes should be taken to make the people aware about the benefit of postgraduate education of the women for the rural area. Among 150 investors 49 are unmarried and 83 are married. Married investors expect high return with high risk. Moreover married investors concerned about future uncertainties and future need first. The majority of the respondents are from the Nuclear family. This implies that in this district the Joint Family system is slowly reducing its practice. If we look into the monthly savings of the respondents, we find that monthly savings are accounted to be very low as because of their low occupational status and low monthly income.

Most of the respondents got the sources of information about various investments avenue through that their family members and banking awareness camp. This information motivated them to become successful investors. There are the various investment avenues available in the market, the majority of the women investors only prefers bank deposits and followed by construction of own buildings/ separate house. Nobody has invested their investment in the mutual fund investments. So, wide awareness must be given regarding the feature of the various types of investments scheme, especially in the mutual fund investments. The objectives of the investment vary from one to another. Most of the investors invest their savings in the objective of 'children's marriage' and 'earning profit', followed by 'personal safety' as their investment objectives. Hence high return and personal safety are the prime motives for investments.

The women earning as ordinary workforces spend and save sufficient money for their future security and financial need. These women may be better financial decision makers if they avoid delay in choosing their right saving/investment avenues. A woman must make a self-evaluation before she starts an investment plan, by permanent reading and tracking the financial and capital market operation, her literacy levels will certainly improve about this field.

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Guest Lecturer in Commerce, Sethupathy Govt. Arts College, Achundanvayal (PO), Ramanathapuram (District) – 623502, Tamil Nadu.]
Asst. Prof. Dept of Commerce with Computer Applications, Caussanel College of Arts and Science, Ramanathapuram (District) – 623523, Tamil Nadu.